

Original Article

Bone Formation Potential of Pomegranate Peel Extract when Used with Implantable Bone Substitutes: An Animal Study

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Pomegranate fruit and its components have been used in Ayurveda for a long time in India in the treatment of osteoporosis. A combination of calcium sulphate, titanium dioxide and pomegranate fruit peel extract has not been tried in the treatment bony defects. Objectives of the study was to compare the bone augmentation potential of two bone substitute materials viz. calcium sulphate - titanium dioxide nano composite and pomegranate peel extract mediated calcium sulphate - titanium dioxide nano composite. Twelve rabbits were selected of which six served as controls and the other six as experimental. Calcium sulphate - titanium dioxide nano composite was implanted in the control group and pomegranate peel extract mediated calcium sulphate - titanium dioxide - nano composite was implanted in the experimental group. Hematologic and alkaline phosphatase evaluation was done at 0, 2, 4 and 12th week. At the end of 4th week three control and three experimental group of animals were euthanised and bone specimens were collected for histologic observations. At the 12th week the remaining rabbits were euthanised and specimens were obtained. Osteoblasts and osteocytes were counted at 4th and 12th week. The results were statistically analysed. Blood cells counts and haemoglobin level showed changes at the selected time intervals. Alkaline phosphatase level responded significantly in the experimental group which can be attributed to the bone augmentation potential of pomegranate peel extract. The mean osteoblast cell count in the 4th week of observation was 55 ± 10.49 % for the control group and 89.50 ± 8.29 % for the experimental group. In the 12th week, the osteoblast cell count was 6.67 ± 2.58 % for the control group and 11.67 ± 2.58 % for the experimental group. The study concluded that pomegranate peel extract has definite stimulatory effect on osteoblasts and enhances bone formation when implanted along with calcium sulphate - titanium dioxide nano composite. Assessment of serum alkaline phosphatase can be used as a bone turn over marker and can be used to evaluate the bone stimulatory and formation potential of implanted materials when they are newly introduced. Osteoblast cell count observed at different time intervals of the experiment validates the bone formation potential assessed through the determination of ALP levels.

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Introduction

Morphological deficiencies of the jaw bones are attributed to automobile accidents, surgical interventions related to benign and malignant neoplasms, congenital abnormalities, periodontal diseases, therapeutic dental extractions and atrophy coincident to advancing age. For the restoration of normal anatomic contour as a requisite to function and aesthetics or for the placement of dental

implants, dentoalveolar reconstruction becomes necessary and with the modern technological advancements like bone grafting, guided bone regeneration, distraction osteogenesis, use of growth factors and stem cells, its possibility and predictability has increased [1-4].

In situations of limited bone availability, replacement of teeth using dental implants become extremely difficult. Bone augmentation is indicated to overcome this situation and use of bone grafts become relevant in this context. Popularly used bone grafts consist of materials of natural or synthetic origin and which are implanted into the deficit site to achieve morphologic

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restoration. Adequately positioned grafts, act as a scaffold for the newly formed bone. Most of the grafts have pronounced bone healing capability and osteoconductivity. A large heterogeneous group of alloplastic materials consisting of calcium phosphate, calcium carbonate, Calcium sulphate, Titanium dioxide, bioactive glasses and polymers are used for the bone augmentation purpose. Calcium sulphate (CaSO_4) and titanium dioxide (TiO_2) are emerging as promising graft materials to address defects of oral and maxillofacial region. Calcium sulphate, exhibits biocompatibility and resorbability and that allows for gradual replacement by native bone tissue. Its osteoconductive properties facilitate bone regeneration while providing structural support during the healing process. It has been reported that osteoblasts show particular affinity to calcium sulphate hemi hydrate [5,6].

Titanium dioxide is known for its inertness and favourable biocompatibility profile. It serves as a successful scaffold material for bone regeneration. Its porous nature allows for cell adhesion, proliferation and vascularization which are considered to be essential for successful regeneration of bone. Porous titanium granules have been tried in dental extraction sockets, augmentation of maxillary sinus, peri implant defects and in augmentation of jaw bones. When used together as a composite, calcium sulphate and titanium dioxide create a synergistic potential, combining the resorbable and osteoconductive properties of calcium sulphate with the biocompatibility of titanium dioxide, thereby promoting efficient bone repair and regeneration in jaw bone defects. In the present study, calcium sulphate - titanium dioxide nano composite was used as a control material [7-11].

In India, jaw bone deficits should be viewed in the context of the larger picture perceived amongst the senior citizens. There is a high prevalence of osteoporosis in Indian women of different age groups (8-62%) and in Indian men above the age of fifty years (8.5-24.6%). The dynamic nature of bone and its precise remodelling regulated by osteoblasts and osteoclasts is well documented. When the regulation ceases or when the bone turn over becomes low, it finally ends up with osteoporosis which is characterized by low bone mass and defective micro architecture leading to fragility fractures. The traditional focus on treatment using calcium and vitamin D is becoming more inclusive by incorporating multitude of nutrients like polyphenolic compounds such as flavonoids. These nutrients control osteoporosis by inhibiting osteoclast differentiation and by stimulating osteoblast formation [12-15].

Pomegranate (*Punica granatum*) has been identified as a rich source of micronutrients and it occupied a prominent place in ancient medicine of many cultures and in India. Ayurveda has identified its therapeutic potential viz. antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and bone stimulatory effects, years ago and presently it is getting reinvented. The beneficial effects of pomegranate peel are rated to be higher than that of the edible portions of the fruit. The peel contains polyphenols such as punicalagin, flavonoids and hydrolysable tannins [16,17]. Literature provides definitive evidence on the use of pomegranate and its extracts for the treatment of osteoarthritis, osteoporosis and related illnesses. Most of the studies have referred to the consumption of pomegranate and its derivatives to be used in bone remodelling. It was reported that consumption of pomegranate juice or pomegranate peel extract induced bone formation through decreased inflammation and by reducing the oxidative stress [18]. Pomegranate peel extract is reported to have osteoinductive properties due to the presence of the polyphenolic compounds in large quantities [19]. The

osteoinductive potential of pomegranate peel extract is evident when it is consumed therapeutically. Pomegranate seed oil which is rich in phenolic compounds, in combination with gelatin sponge when applied locally was found to have enhanced bone regeneration capability [20]. So far pomegranate peel extract has not been tried in conjunction with a bone graft material to evaluate its locally acting capability. Most of the currently used methods of bone regeneration exhibit satisfactory outcome. There are limitations experienced in procuring the material and the cost effectiveness. Presently available synthetic bone substitutes cannot claim fully matching biological and mechanical equivalence to bone. Hence there is a necessity to develop novel alternatives for bone regeneration [21]. In this context, the present experiment using animal models was taken up to compare the bone augmentation potential of two graft materials viz. 1. Calcium sulphate - titanium dioxide nano composite 2. Pomegranate peel extract mediated calcium sulphate - titanium dioxide nano composite (PPE CaSO_4 TiO_2).

Materials and Methods

The present experimental study using animal models were designed to evaluate the bone augmentation potential of two graft materials viz. 1. Calcium sulphate - Titanium dioxide nano composite, 2. Pomegranate peel extract mediated Calcium sulphate- Titanium dioxide-nano composite.

Preparation of CaSO_4 TiO_2 nano composite

0.5g of CaSO_4 was mixed in 25mL distilled water it was then kept in a magnetic stirrer at 600 rpm for 24 hrs. Another solution of 0.35g of titanium oxide mixed in 25mL distilled water was kept in magnetic stirrer at 600 rpm for 24hr. After 24 hrs both solutions were mixed together to form CaSO_4 - TiO_2 nano composite solution. This mixture was kept in magnetic stirrer at 700 rpm for 48 hours. The nano composite solution was centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 10 minutes; the pellet was collected and supernatant was discarded. The collected pellet was dried in a hot air oven at 80°C to obtain CaSO_4 - TiO_2 nano composite powder

Preparation of pomegranate peel extract (PPE)

Peel of the pomegranate was harvested and air dried. It was then coarsely powdered and the extract was obtained in ethyl alcohol using Soxhlet extraction process.

Green synthesis of PPE mediated CaSO_4

Green synthesis of PPE mediated CaSO_4 was performed by dissolving 0.5gm of CaSO_4 in 25ml of distilled water. To this mixture, 25ml of filtered PPE was added. It was then placed in a magnetic stirrer operating at 600 rpm for 24hrs. The nano particles were then collected and the supernatant liquid was discarded.

Green synthesis of PPE mediated TiO_2 nanoparticles

0.35gm of titanium oxide was weighed and mixed with 25ml of distilled water, to which 25ml of filtered PPE was added. It was then kept in a magnetic stirrer which operated at 600 rpm for 48 hours.

Preparation of PPE mediated calcium sulphate - titanium dioxide nano composite

PPE mediated CaSO_4 nano particles and PPE mediated TiO_2 nano particles were combined together to get 100ml of PPE mediated CaSO_4 TiO_2 nano composite solution. This solution was kept in

magnetic stirrer for 48 hrs. After 48 hrs, the nanoparticles were collected and the supernatant liquid was discarded.

PPE mediated $\text{CaSO}_4\text{-TiO}_2$ nano particle powder was mixed with distilled water (water-powder ratio of 0.6) to get a smooth mixture. An elastomeric mould was prepared by embedding a stainless-steel rod of 10 mm length and 2 mm diameter in elastomeric impression material. The mix was filled into the mould and vibrated. After setting, the cylinders were sectioned and finished to obtain specimens measuring 6 x 2 mm. The same procedure was followed for $\text{CaSO}_4\text{-TiO}_2$ nano composite. These specimens were later implanted in the experimental animals.

Cytotoxic evaluation

In vitro cytotoxic effect determination of pomegranate peel extract was done by MTT Assay using L929-fibroblast cells. The cells were observed after a period of 24 hours of treatment using an inverted phase contrast tissue culture microscope (Olympus CKX41 with Optika Pro5 CCD camera). Any detectable change in the morphology of the cells, such as rounding or shrinking of cells, granulation and vacuolization in the cytoplasm of the cells were considered as indicators of cytotoxicity. The test material was cleared for implantation, once it was proved that there is no cytotoxic effect.

Implantation procedure in rabbits

Twelve New Zealand white strain rabbits weighing approximately 2 kg were selected and divided equally into two groups – control and experimental. All the experimental animals were acclimatized for a period of one week. Physical examination of rabbits was performed by a trained veterinarian and the weight of the animals were verified using accurate electronic scales. Prior to implantation, blood samples were collected to find out complete blood count and serum alkaline phosphatase levels.

Implantation procedure was carried out in the Department of Veterinary Surgery and Radiology, College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Mannuthy, Thrissur, Kerala. The Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals issued permission to conduct the experiments (CPCSEA No.328/GO/Re/S/01/CPCSEA, dated 26/08/16). All the procedures were

Figure 2: Preparation of defect for the placement of implant material

Figure 3: Graft material packed into the osseous defect

Figure 1: Skin incision on the hind leg

carried out with the approval of the CPCSEA, New Delhi and after obtaining the approval of Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC).

The surgical procedure was carried out under anaesthesia, induced by intramuscular injection of ketamine hydrochloride, 35 mg per kg body weight and diazepam inj. 0.5 mg per kg body weight. The surgical site was prepared by removing the hair. The skin was scrubbed using antiseptic solution - 5 % povidone iodine and 2% chlorhexidine. Craniolateral incision of 2.5cm was made on the dorsal aspect of the thigh. The muscles were dissected to expose the cortex of the femur of both the hind limbs of the rabbits. Two osseous defects of 2 mm diameter were prepared 2 cm apart on each leg with a tungsten carbide bur attached to a slow speed micromotor hand piece (Marathon micromotor 800 rpm) with profuse irrigation using normal saline (figures 1-3).

In the control group which consisted of six rabbits, titanium dioxide - calcium sulphate nano composite was implanted in both the left and right femur. In the experimental group of six rabbits, pomegranate peel extract mediated titanium dioxide - calcium sulphate nano composite was implanted. The cylinders of the composite were positioned in the osseous defects and were stabilised by condensing the same material around it. The muscles were closed using resorbable sutures - polyglactin 910 sutures (Vicryl) followed by suturing of the skin using nylon. Surgical dressing was placed over the sutured tissue and the hind limbs were immobilised.

Standard post-operative care was provided to the animals along with postoperative antibiotic therapy (Ceftriaxone inj. 25 mg body weight intramuscular) and pain management (Butorphanol inj. 0.1 mg per kg body weight intramuscular). Individual animals were identified by tattoo marks placed on the animal's ear. In addition to this, each animal cage was marked by label which carried the title of the study, group, sex, date of initiation and completion of the experiment.

Post implantation phase

The animals body weight, pulse rate, respiratory rate, feed intake, behavioural changes were observed following the implantation. Blood samples were collected at four observation periods namely baseline (On the day of surgery before undertaking the procedure), post operatively on 2nd, 4th and 12th week for assessing complete blood count and serum alkaline phosphatase level.

At the end of 4th week, three animals from the control and three from the experimental group were euthanised, observing standard protocol. The sites of implantation were identified and macroscopically examined for any evidence of tissue reaction. Radiographic evaluation was also carried out to find out the status of the implanted material. Both the implanted sites were sectioned and stored separately. At the end of 12th week, the remaining three control and three test group animals were euthanised to retrieve the samples along with the femur bone. The samples for histological evaluation were stored in formalin solution.

Histologic evaluation

Decalcification of the bone samples were done using 5% nitric acid for approximately 1-2 weeks. The solution was changed 2 times a day. The specimens were then washed under tap water for 8 hrs. The specimens were fixed in 10% formalin overnight and were dehydrated in acetone for one and half hours and in xylene for half an hour. The specimens were further cleared in xylene for 1 hour, followed by wax impregnation at 60°C for one hour. After embedding the specimens in wax blocks, sections were prepared using microtome and stained using H and E stain. The sections were microscopically evaluated for osteoblast and osteocyte cell count.

Statistical analysis

Data obtained were analysed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) software version 16.0. Quantitative variables were expressed in mean \pm SD and qualitative variables were expressed in percentage. Student t test and Mann-Whitney U test were used to compare the two groups. Null and alternate hypothesis were formulated and p- value less than 0.05 was considered as significant and the null hypothesis was rejected.

Results

Cytotoxic evaluation of pomegranate peel extract was done by MTT Assay using L929-fibroblasts. After an observation period of 24 hours, no detectable change in the morphology of cells was found and the test material was cleared for implantation studies (figures 4,5).

Implantation of graft materials in rabbits

Blood samples were collected from both control and experimental group of animals at the beginning of the experiment and at the end of 2nd, 4th and 12th week and the following data were obtained viz. WBC count, RBC count, Hemoglobin, Platelet count and Alkaline phosphatase. Histologic sections were obtained at the end of 4th week and 12th week. At the end of 4th week, 3 control and 3 experimental animals were euthanized and at the end of 12th week, the remaining 3 control and 3 experimental animals were euthanized

Figure 4: Control specimens showing viable cells in MTT assay

Figure 5: Cells exposed to Pomegranate peel extract -viable cells are seen in MTT assay

Table 1: Mean WBC values observed at different time intervals and comparison between control and experimental groups of animals (x 10³ /µl)

WBC	Control		Experimental		t	p
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Baseline	8.20	0.78	10.03	2.41	1.771	0.107
Week 2	10.42	1.30	12.90	4.70	1.248	0.24
Week 4	12.50	1.55	13.13	0.21	0.7	0.522
Week 12	11.33	0.40	12.10	0.98	1.247	0.28

Table 2: Mean RBC values observed at different time intervals and comparison between control and experimental groups of animals (x 10⁶ /µl)

RBC	Control		Experimental		t	p
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Baseline	4.68	0.91	4.86	0.39	0.428	0.677
Week 2	3.83	0.37	5.07	0.66	4.025	0.002
Week 4	4.23	0.26	5.57	0.27	6.24	0.003
Week 12	4.62	0.33	4.31	0.23	-1.362	0.245

and bone samples were collected for histologic evaluation.

WBC count

The WBC count obtained in the control group at base line, 2nd week, 4th week and 12th week were as follows: 8.20 ± 0.78, 10.42 ± 1.30, 12.50 ± 1.55 and 11.33 ± 0.40 (x 10³/µl). For the experimental group, the values were: 10.03 ± 2.41, 12.90 ± 4.70, 13.13 ± 0.21 and 12.10 ± 0.98 respectively. The WBC count showed an increase from base line to 4th week and in the 12th week a slight decline, both in the control and experimental groups. The values were within normal limits and the difference between the control and experimental groups was not significant (table 1).

Table 3: Mean Hemoglobin values observed at different time intervals and comparison between control and experimental groups of animals (g/dl)

Hb / different time intervals	Experimental		Control		t	p
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Baseline	12.37	0.97	11.78	2.24	0.586	0.571
Week 2	12.95	0.64	11.15	0.80	4.311	0.002
Week 4	13.27	0.40	11.93	0.35	4.313	0.013
Week 12	12.87	0.49	11.95	2.77	0.562	0.604

Table 4: Mean Platelet count values observed at different time intervals and comparison between control and experimental groups of animals (x 10³ /µl)

PLT	Experimental		Control		t	p
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Baseline	236.83	112.97	318.50	68.54	-1.514	0.161
Week 2	230.83	120.20	393.83	121.22	-2.339	0.041
Week 4	336.33	43.62	347.67	20.55	-0.407	0.705
Week 12	245.33	79.26	224.00	7.94	0.464	0.667

RBC count

The RBC counts for the control group were as follows: 4.68 ± 0.91, 3.83 ± 0.37, 4.23 ± 0.26 and 4.62 ± 0.33 (x 10⁶/µl) at the time intervals of base line, 2, 4 and 12 weeks. For the experimental group the counts were 4.86 ± 0.39, 5.07 ± 0.66, 5.57 ± 0.27 and 4.31 ± 0.23 for the respective observation period. The control group values showed a decrease in the 2nd week when compared to the base line. In the 4th and 12th week the values showed an increase. In the experimental group, the values showed a steady increase till the 4th week. In the 12th week, the values decreased. In both the groups, the values were within normal range. Excepting 2nd and 4th week, the other two groups did not show significant difference between the control and experimental animals (table 2).

Haemoglobin

The estimated haemoglobin values of control group at base line, 2nd, 4th and 12th week were 11.78 ± 2.24, 11.15 ± 0.80, 11.93 ± 0.35 and 11.95 ± 2.77 (g/dl). Respective values for the experimental group were 12.37 ± 0.97, 12.95 ± 0.64, 13.27 ± 0.40 and 12.87 ± 0.49 (g/dl). There was no statistically significant difference between the control and test group values except in those of the second week (table 3).

Platelet count

The mean platelet count observed at base line, 2nd, 4th and 12th week were 318.50 ± 68.54, 393.83 ± 121.22, 347.67 ± 20.55 and 224.0 ± 7.94 (x 10³/µl) for the control group. The respective values for the experimental group were 236.83 ± 112.97, 230.83 ± 120.20, 336.33 ± 43.62 and 245.33 ± 79.26 (x 10³/µl). The platelet count showed an increase from the base line, in the 4th week and came back to normal level in the 12th week. There was no statistically significant difference between the control and experimental groups while comparing the platelet count (table 4).

Alkaline phosphatase

The level of alkaline phosphatase was estimated at the base line, 2nd, 4th and 12th week for the control group animals and the values were 360.75 ± 36.01, 192.75 ± 57.901, 261.1 ± 43.74 and 226.13 ± 14.57 (IU/L). For the experimental group the values estimated were 361.80 ± 40.10, 255.166 ± 36.79, 395.3 ± 16.781 and 267.6 ± 11.5 (IU/L).

The mean alkaline phosphatase values of experimental group showed a fluctuation as follows: From base line to 2nd week there was a decrease and in the 4th week there was an increase. In the 12th week there was again a decrease. In contrast, the control group showed a decrease in the 2nd week and afterwards the values increased steadily upto 12th week (table 5).

Table 5: Mean Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) values observed at different time intervals and comparison between control and experimental groups of animals (IU/L)

ALP	Experimental		Control		t	P
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Baseline	361.80	40.10	360.75	36.01	0.04	0.96
Week 2	255.17	36.79	192.75	57.90	2.23	0.024
Week 4	395.30	16.78	261.10	43.74	4.96	0.007
Week 12	267.60	11.50	226.13	14.57	3.83	0.018

Table 6: Mean and standard deviation of osteoblasts and osteocytes count observed at different time intervals and comparison between control group and test group (%)

Type of specimen	Cells	Percentage value of cells 4 th week	Percentage value of cells 12 th week	t-value Experimental/ Control	p-value
Control	Osteoblasts	55.00 ± 10.49	6.67 ± 2.58	3.354	0.007
Experimental	Osteoblasts	89.50 ± 8.29	11.67 ± 2.58	6.322	0.000
Control	Osteocytes	45.00 ± 10.49	93.33 ± 2.58	-3.354	0.007
Experimental	Osteocytes	10.50 ± 8.29	88.33 ± 2.58	-6.322	0.000

Osteoblasts and osteocytes

The animals were euthanised at the end of the 4th week and 12th week to obtain the bone samples for estimating the osteoblasts and osteocytes and recorded in percentage of the total cells counted. The mean osteoblast cell count in the 4th week of observation was 55 ± 10.49% for the control group and 89.50 ± 8.29% for the experimental group. The mean osteocyte cell count in the 4th week was as follows: 45.00±10.49% (control) and 10.50±8.29% (experimental). In the 12th week, the osteoblast cell count was 6.67±2.58% for the control group and 11.67±2.58 % for the experimental group; the osteocyte cell count was 93.33±2.58% for the control group and 88.33±2.58% for the experimental group. The difference noticed between control and experimental groups as well as between the 4th and 12th week was significant (table 6), (figures 6,7).

Discussion

Augmented bone regeneration is necessitated in many maxillofacial surgical procedures where the first and preferred choice is always autologous bone because it has the most ideal properties like osteoinduction, osteogenesis and osteoconduction. Sourcing of bone grafts has found to be extremely difficult and the search for substitutes has become very active. Most of these materials are made of natural or synthetic biomaterials and which serve as scaffolds favoring migration, proliferation and differentiation of

bone cells. Hydroxy apatite, calcium phosphate, calcium sulphate, titanium dioxide and glass ceramics are some of the materials which popularly find a place in the bone regeneration arena. These materials receive acceptability because they are osteoconductive, biocompatible, bioresorbable, having structural similarity to bone, show minimal fibrotic reaction, user friendly and cost effective [22, 23].

The WBC count was evaluated before the start of the experiment and at the end of the 4th and 12th week. At the end of 4th week, the values increased and at the end of 12th week the values declined in both the control and experimental groups. This is due to an inflammatory response to the implantation and it comes back towards normalcy when the healing process progresses. Implantation of bone substitute can alter the local blood supply as part of inflammatory response and the overall systemic RBC count remains relatively stable. In the present study, the values fluctuated and by the end of 12th week, the RBC count came to normalcy both in the control and experimental groups. Hemoglobin values also showed a pattern similar to the RBC count. Minor fluctuations in hemoglobin levels occur in the post operative period and the fluctuations get resolved when the healing process progresses (table 1-3).

It has been observed that stress can alter different haematological parameters. In rabbits, an increase in adrenaline levels (acute stress) induces lymphocytosis. Prolonged stress, such as transportation, unfamiliar noises, smell, chronic pain, and poor environment, can

Figure 6: Microscopic view of osteoblasts

Figure 7: Microscopic view of osteoblasts

induce lymphopenia, and leucocytosis. Menthou et al. observed that pomegranate juice (PJ) consumption resulted in a significant increase in red blood cell count and haemoglobin levels. Increased content of polyphenols in PJ may have prevented RBC destruction due to reduced oxidative stress. Flavonoids serve an important role in preventing oxidation of haemoglobin by its binding property and inhibit oxidation of the haemoglobin molecule.

After the implantation, the platelet count showed marginal increase up to the 4th week and afterwards the values came back to normalcy. Between the control and experimental groups, there was no significant difference. Platelets play a crucial role in hemostasis and wound healing. The increase in the count can be attributed to platelet activation, inflammation and tissue repair process. Changes in platelet count are usually short-lived and normalize as the healing process advances (table 4).

Alkaline phosphatase is an enzyme closely associated with osteoblastic activity and bone formation. When the new bone is formed and gets mineralized, the ALP values increase and gradually get declined along with the progress in bone remodeling. The ALP values of control group at the base line were 360.75 ± 36.01 and at the end of 12th week it was 226.13 ± 14.57 (IU/L). For the experimental group the values were 361.80 ± 40.10 , 267.6 ± 11.5 (IU/L) respectively. The values observed at the end of the 12th week clearly indicate that pomegranate peel extract has a positive role in enhancing the osteoblastic activity (table 5).

Spilmont et al. reported that mice fed with pomegranate seed oil elicited significant increase in alkaline phosphatase activity in osteoblast like cells [26]. Sipani et al evaluated the changes of serum alkaline phosphatase level during healing of diaphyseal fractures of long bones in adults and found a significant rise in serum alkaline phosphatase level in the third week of healing. They concluded that rise in the level of serum ALP indicates an increased osteoblastic activity [27]. Camassa et al. mentioned that, Bone ALP has been used as a biomarker due to its high sensitivity in bone formation. It is produced by osteoblasts and is involved in the calcification of bone matrix through the hydrolysis of phosphate esters on the osteoblast cell surface, resulting in a high extracellular inorganic phosphate concentration [28]. Nazht et al. and Bhati et al. have observed that an increase in serum ALP serves as a bio marker that indicates fracture healing. During fracture healing stages, the weekly elevation of serum ALP enzyme had a positive correlation between osteoblast cells activation and differentiation with new bone formation. ALP is elevated 10 to 14 days after fracture due to proliferation and activation of osteoblasts cells on the newly formed trabecular bone surface and that lead to osteoid formation and enhance mineralization [29,30]. The observations in the present study fall in line with the remarks of the research workers cited above. Authors of the present study observed that the serum alkaline phosphatase level showed maximum increase in the 4th week of healing in both control and experimental groups. The test group showed a greater increase than the control group and was statistically significant. This increase in ALP in the experimental group is possibly due to the presence of Pomegranate peel extract in the test material.

Histologic evaluation of osteoblasts and osteocytes

Both the control and experimental group of animals were euthanized on completion of the 4th and 12th week of healing period and bone cell count (osteoblasts and osteocytes) was carried out. In the control group, during the 4th week of observation the mean osteoblastic count was 55 ± 10.49 and in the 12th week the

count significantly decreased to 6.67 ± 2.58 ($p < 0.00001$). In the experimental group, the mean osteoblastic count during the 4th week was 89.50 ± 8.29 and in the 12th week the count significantly decreased to 11.67 ± 2.58 (p value 0.00001) (figure 6).

When the time dependent comparison of bone cells was made between the 4th and 12th week, Osteoblasts increased in number in the 4th week subsequent to the surgical intervention in both control and experimental groups. In the 12th week, the osteoblast count decreased in both the groups, possibly because of the conversion of osteoblasts to osteocytes. Comparison of osteoblast count between the control and experimental groups endorses the enhanced bone formation potential of the test material (PPE).

The histological evaluation conducted by Mohammed et al. also had similar observations with pomegranate seed oil extracts [31]. Monsefi et al. determined the effects of pomegranate juice extract on chondrogenesis and osteogenesis in mouse embryos and found out that mice treated with pomegranate juice extract showed an increase in bone calcium content. They also concluded that pomegranate could enhance bone formation [32]. Young Ho Kim et al. evaluated the effect of pomegranate extract on osteoblastic differentiation and tumour necrosis factor (TNF- α -) stimulated production of interleukin-6 and nitric oxide using the pre-osteoblastic target cell line and concluded that pomegranate extract promoted the function of osteoblasts and plays an important role in bone remodeling [33].

Histologic evaluation - osteocyte

The mean osteocyte count observed in the 4th week was 45 ± 10.49 in the control group and in the 12th week the count increased to 93.33 ± 2.58 . In the experimental group during the 4th week, the mean osteocyte count was 10.50 ± 8.29 and in the 12th week, the count increased to 88.33 ± 2.58 . Statistical analysis showed a significant difference between the values obtained at different time intervals ($p < 0.0001$). Lesser osteocyte count in the experimental group is suggestive of higher osteoblastic activity. As mentioned in the previous section, osteoblasts become osteocytes at the end of bone formation period. Significantly high osteoblast count observed in the 4th week in the experimental group is suggestive of the osteogenic potential of the PPE. The osteocyte count at the 12th week is almost similar in both the experimental and control groups which is suggestive of new bone getting converted to mature bone (figure 7).

Corinne Metzger and Anand Narayanan reviewed the role of osteocytes and stated that "Osteocytes coordinate the actions of osteoblasts and osteoclasts. Osteocytes express and release proteins that signal osteoblasts, osteoclasts, and other bone-residing cells to respond to environmental changes. Osteocytes express important factors for the maintenance of mineral homeostasis." In inflammatory bone loss, osteocytes have an important role and considered to be targets while treating the bone loss. Low grade inflammation can be considered as beneficial in the process of fracture healing. In the present study, the status of osteocytes is maintained within the normal time frame and PPE had only positive effects on the bone cells [34].

Franz-Odendaal et al. have explored on the osteoblast-to-osteocyte transformation during intramembranous ossification from both morphological and molecular perspectives. The osteoblasts on the bone surface which are destined for burial and to become osteocytes slow down matrix production compared to the neighboring osteoblasts, which continue to produce bone matrix. The slowed

Figure 8: Radiographic evaluation of the implanted site

down cells will get engulfed in the matrix produced by the active cells. The osteoblast-osteocyte ratio changes in the initial and later stages of bone production can be explained in this context [35]. Manolagas et al. suggested that the fully differentiated osteoblasts produce and secrete proteins that constitute the bone matrix which is subsequently mineralized. Some osteoblasts are eventually buried within lacunae of mineralized matrix and these cells are termed osteocytes. Osteocytes are the most abundant cell type in bone: it is estimated that osteocytes are ten times more than the osteoblasts. The present study also had matching observations [36].

From the results obtained, the present study did not find any significant change in the blood parameters which suggest that the addition of pomegranate peel extract did not alter the physiologic profile. The significant change in ALP values indicate the increased osteoblastic activity; enhanced bone formation and the positive role of PPE.

Radiographic assessment revealed that the graft material could be identified in the initial phases of the experiment and by the 12th week the radio opacity decreased which indicates adequate bone healing that has occurred at the implanted site (figure 8).

Conclusion

Pomegranate peel extract has definite stimulatory effect on osteoblasts and enhances bone formation when implanted along with calcium sulphate - titanium dioxide nanocomposite. Assessment of serum alkaline phosphatase can be used as a bone turn over marker and can be used to evaluate the bone stimulatory and formation potential of implanted materials when they are newly introduced. Osteoblast cell count observed at different time intervals of the experiment validates the bone formation potential assessed through the determination of ALP levels. PPE can be safely used along with bone substitute materials and the experiment proves its bone augmentation efficacy. This experiment provides evidence for the local effectiveness of PPE. However, its systemic efficiency has already been proved. The blood cell count variations observed at different stages of the study can be considered as an inflammatory response and at the same time it indicates the physiologic profile of the PPE.

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